

Empowering Women: Menstruation, Public Health and Quality of life.

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Abstract

Menstrual health is a state of complete physical, mental, and social wellbeing and not merely absence of menstrual problems. Menstrual health is firmly on the global agenda today. WHO calls for menstrual health to be recognized, framed and addressed as a health and human rights issue, not a hygiene issue. Data suggests that about 2.3 crores of girls missed their school on the onset of menstruation during 2020-2021. Gender inequality and stereotypes prevailing in the society, which affects the women's quality of life during menstruation. Most of the women experience problems such as physical, psychological, socio-cultural issues including depression, anxiety, mood swings, intense pain etc. As per available literature a woman menstruates about 38 years of her life leading to various changes in her life.

The objective of this paper is to identify various physical and psychological problems faced by females during menstruation and also analyze the association between menstruation and its effects on women's quality of life during the process of the shedding of the uterine lining on a regular monthly predictable period.

The data suggests that the biological part of the menstruation is being covered in the biology textbooks at schools, but not cover the problems being faced by the girls and women in India due to socio-cultural factors such as social stigma and social taboos. Most of the girls reported that the first experience of menstruation was painful because they did not then understand what was happening. Adolescent girls who have menstrual issues such as cramps, tiredness, backache, swelling abdomen and painful breasts, miss their school and college and resulting the restricted growth and associated risks.

Keywords: Social Wellbeing, Social Stigma, Anxiety, Cramps.

Introduction-

Menstrual health is a critical yet often overlooked aspect of public health. Defined by the ability to manage menstruation safely, hygienically and with dignity, menstrual health intersects

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with gender equality ,education and economic development .Globally ,millions of people who menstruate face barriers such as stigma, inadequate access to products ,and lack of education despite its profound implications on physical ,mental and social wellbeing ,menstrual health remains a neglected public health issue ,requiring urgent attention to foster sustainable development and improve the quality of life. **WHO calls for Menstrual health to be recognized, framed and addressed as a health and human rights issue, not a hygiene issue.** Health in context of physical, Psychological, and social dimensions. Secondly, Menstrual health means that women and girls have access to information and education about it, to the menstrual products they need, water, sanitation and disposal facilities, to emphatic care when needed, to live, study and work in an environment in which menstruation is seen as positive and healthy not something to be ashamed and to fully participate in work and social activities. Thirdly, to ensure that these activities are included in the relevant sectoral work plans and budgets, and their performance is measured.

Governments are beginning to act, but they need to do much more-

Some governments have removed taxes on menstrual products. Many countries have put in place laws and policies for medical leave during menstruation.

Parents, especially the mothers do not educate their daughters about various aspects of menstruation .the girls are not motivated to take this event lightly .inadequate knowledge ,misconceptions and wrong ideas lead to undue fear ,anxiety and undesirable attitudes in the minds of girls. The studies recommended a planned educational programme to enlighten young girls for healthy practice on attaining menarche.

Some studies have also concluded that depression and mood changes often show up in the days before and onset of menstruation, but they don't automatically disappear once it begins. They can linger for few days, if not longer some people also experience depression after their period ends.

Menstruation is a normal physiological process but is frequently complicated by premenstrual disturbances. School absenteeism and interference with life activities /quality of life are some of the reported consequences of menstrual disorder.

Need for study-

Menstruation is a natural biological process that affects nearly half of the global population at some point in their lives. Despite its universality, menstruation remains stigmatized, poorly understood, and inadequately addressed in public health policies. Women and girls, particularly in low-resource settings, face significant barriers to menstrual hygiene management, which negatively impacts their health, education, and overall well-being. The need for this study arises from the urgent requirement to address these barriers, ensuring that menstruation is no longer a source of discrimination, health risks, or reduced quality of life.

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Access to menstrual hygiene products, proper sanitation, and education on menstrual health is a public health priority. Poor menstrual health management has been linked to infections, reproductive health complications, and mental distress. Additionally, societal stigma and misinformation contribute to gender-based inequalities, restricting women's participation in education, work, and social activities. The economic burden associated with menstrual hygiene products also exacerbates financial disparities, making it difficult for marginalized groups to access necessary resources.

This study is crucial in highlighting the intersection of menstruation, public health, and women's empowerment. By examining policies, cultural attitudes, and infrastructural gaps, the research aims to propose sustainable solutions that promote menstrual equity. Addressing menstrual health as a fundamental public health issue will contribute to improved educational outcomes, economic participation, and enhanced quality of life for women and girls. Through evidence-based recommendations, this study seeks to inform policymakers, healthcare providers, and communities about the importance of inclusive menstrual health initiatives, ultimately fostering gender equality and societal progress.

Early Studies on Menstruation and Public Health (2000–2010)

Sommer (2000) – This study explored menstrual hygiene management (MHM) in developing countries and its impact on adolescent girls' education. It highlighted the role of poor sanitation in school absenteeism. **Mahon & Fernandes (2002)** – Examined the lack of menstrual hygiene awareness in South Asia and its relation to infections and reproductive health issues. **Dolan et al. (2005)** – Investigated the effect of menstrual stigma on school attendance in Uganda, revealing that inadequate MHM facilities contributed to dropouts. **Garg et al. (2007)** – Focused on menstrual practices in rural India, emphasizing the cultural restrictions placed on menstruating women and their negative psychosocial effects. **Hennegan & Montgomery (2009)** – This study systematically reviewed menstrual health interventions and their outcomes on women's health and well-being.

Menstrual Hygiene and Societal Impact (2011–2015)

House et al. (2012) – Provided an extensive review of menstrual hygiene challenges in low-income settings, emphasizing the need for policy interventions. **McMahon et al. (2013)** – Explored social stigma and the silence around menstruation in African communities, leading to negative self-perceptions in adolescent girls. **Chothe et al. (2014)** – Conducted research in India, identifying a significant gap in menstrual education and its impact on reproductive health. **Sommer et al. (2014)** – Evaluated menstrual health interventions in Tanzania and their effectiveness in reducing school absenteeism. **Montgomery et al. (2015)** – Investigated the psychological impact of menstrual stigma and found a strong link between poor MHM and decreased self-esteem in young girls.

Policy Changes and Global Health Initiatives (2016–2020)

Sumpter & Torondel (2016) – Conducted a systematic review on menstrual hygiene interventions, highlighting their positive impact on school retention. **Hennegan et al. (2017)** – Explored the role of menstrual health in gender equality and suggested policy-level interventions to integrate menstrual health into public health agendas. **Phillips-Howard et al. (2017)** – Investigated the effectiveness of providing free sanitary products in improving girls’ school participation in Kenya. **Das et al. (2018)** – Focused on menstrual poverty and its economic burden on women from low-income backgrounds. **Geertz et al. (2019)** – Identified gaps in menstrual hygiene product availability and affordability across different regions.

Recent Developments and Future Directions (2021–Present)

Sharma et al. (2021) – Examined the impact of digital platforms in spreading menstrual awareness and their effectiveness in breaking taboos. **Chandra-Mouli & Patel (2022)** – Highlighted the role of menstrual education programs in improving adolescent health outcomes. **United Nations (2022)** – Published a global report on menstrual equity, urging governments to integrate menstrual health into public health policies. **Benshaw-Tolonen et al. (2023)** – Studied the impact of menstrual leave policies and workplace productivity, suggesting positive outcomes for gender equity. **Hennegan et al. (2024)** – The latest research discussing sustainable menstrual health solutions and their role in achieving the UN’s Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Methodology - A comprehensive search of published literature using Google scholar, PubMed, SCOPUS, Publications from reputable organizations like WHO, UNICEF and other databases to identify studies examining the relationship between menstruation and quality of life. Only studies focusing on menstruation and its effect on quality of life and related menstrual disorders were included in the current review.

Result and discussion

Menstrual problems are common among females. School and College going girls suffers a lot but the impact of menstrual morbidities and its effect on quality of life has been poorly studied. Understanding the impact on quality of life is an important measure to better understand the impact of health problems.

Studying menstrual morbidities and it effect quality of life of female is significant in various reasons. Understanding menstrual morbidities help to identify common issues that affect females’ life in various ways by addressing these issues healthcare provider can improve overall well-being and reduce the long-term complication. Studying knowledge, attitude, beliefs and practice menstrual health in college girls can highlight gap in education and awareness. This information will help to promote better practices, reduce myths and stigma related to menstruation.

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It also impacts academic performance due to discomfort, pain, and psychological distress. By understanding these challenges, educational institutions can implement various supportive measures like counselling services in school and colleges to help student manage their menstrual health issues. It will also help in promoting positive attitudes and providing psychological support can improve mental health outcomes. It will also help to empower girls to take charge of their own health by following a healthy lifestyle and seeking medical care whenever required.

Data can also be beneficial for future policy making, empowering individuals and advocating policy that prioritize menstrual health equity.

Research gap-

Despite growing recognition of the importance of menstrual health, several research gaps persist:

Cultural and Regional variations-there is a lack of comparative studies exploring cultural and regional influences on menstrual health practices, stigmas and intervention.

Long term impacts-few longitudinal studies investigate the long-term health and social consequences of inadequate menstrual health, including its impact on education, mental health and economic productivity.

Environmental impact: while disposable menstrual products dominate the market, there is limited research on sustainable alternatives and the environment implication of menstrual waste.

Intersectionality -insufficient attention is given to the intersection of menstrual health with factors like disability, socioeconomic status and humanitarian crises.

Recommendation for future Research and Policy

Intersectionality

Research should explore how menstruation intersects various other factors such as caste, religion, race, cultural factors and disability which affect women's quality of life.

Male involvement

Future research should also explore the role of men and boys in menstrual health education and advocacy. Engaging men can create a healthy environment which can reduce stigma related to menstruation.

Policy evaluation

More research is needed to evaluate the effectiveness of programs particularly in low and middle economic countries. This includes assessing the sustainability of various programs related to menstrual health.

Conclusion

The impact of menstruation on women's quality of life is a complex issue that spans both science and society. Physical symptoms, psychological challenges and socio-economic barriers combine to shape women's experiences during menstruation, often limiting their ability to fully engage in daily life.

While progress has been made in addressing the impact of menstruation on women's quality of life, still there are many challenges faced by a girl or women during these days by adopting a multifaceted approach that include all the aspect of female health we can improve the various health outcomes and prepare a female to cope up with menstrual issues. We can work together towards a future where menstruation is no longer a barrier to women's health, education and empowerment. to achieve this a comprehensive approach that integrates scientific research, social advocacy and policy reform is imperative.

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